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МОДЕРНІЗАЦІЯ ДЕРЖАВНОГО УПРАВЛІННЯ ГРУЗІЇ. Е-УРЯД

Широке і ефективне впровадження інформаційно-комунікаційних технологій (ІКТ) в рамках концепції електронного уряду (ЕГ) є частиною комплексу інновацій в державному управлінні. У даній статті розглянуті дослідження впровадження ЕГ як інструменту державного управління на основі досвіду зарубіжних країн. Автор розглядає рівень розвитку ЕГ в різних регіонах, порівнює темпи розвитку і з'ясовує причини нерівномірного застосування ЕГ в практиці державного управління.

У даній статті основну увагу приділяється основній ідеї проекту ЕГ в контексті соціальних, економічних і політичних змін, викликаних впровадженням інформаційних технологій, а також появою попиту на розширення інформаційної відкритості і зростанням потреб.

Якість державних послуг розглядається як фактор руху до сучасної моделі демократії, яка включає вільний доступ до інформації та можливість брати участь в управлінні державними і недержавними інститутами для всіх громадян.

У статті автор демонструє результати аналізу умов реалізації ЕГ, що вимагають спільних зусиль державного апарату, громадських організацій, представників бізнесу та громадян. Також враховуються причини опору впровадженню ЕГ. Крім того, стаття знайомить з етапами процесів форматування та розвитку ЕГ, аналізує громадську думку про це явище всередині країни і в глобальному суспільстві, досліджує взаємозв'язок між впровадженням ЕГ і віковим віком громадян.

Автор розглядає умови, які необхідні для продуктивного використання Інтернет-технологій в політиці, досліджує механізми стимулювання громадян для формування громадянської позиції та розуміння переваг використання ІКТ для реалізації своїх політичних прав і інтересів.

На закінчення зроблено висновок, що для ефективної реалізації концепції електронного уряду необхідно враховувати не тільки технологічні і фінансові можливості суспільства, але і тип місцевої політичної системи і рівень політичної культури, а також доступність інформації та освіти.

Ключові слова: електронний уряд, держава, управління, ІКТ, Інтернет, портал.

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Modernization of government administration of Georgia. E-government

Wide and effective implementation of information and communication technologies (ICT) within the framework of the concept of electronic government (EG) is part of a complex of innovations in public administration. This article examines the study of the introduction of EG as a tool of public administration based on the experience of foreign countries. The author examines the

level of development of the EG in different regions, compares the rates of development, and clarifies the reasons for the uneven use of the EG in the practice of public administration.

This article focuses on the main idea of the EG project in the context of social, economic, and political changes caused by the introduction of information technology, as well as the emerging demand for increased information transparency and growing needs.

The quality of public services is seen as a factor in the movement towards a modern model of democracy, which includes free access to information and the ability to take part in the management of state and non-state institutions for all citizens.

In the article the author demonstrates the results of the analysis of the conditions for the implementation of the EG, requiring joint efforts of the state apparatus, public organizations, business representatives, and citizens. The reasons for resistance to the introduction of EG are also taken into account. In addition, the article introduces the stages of the processes of formatting and development of the EG, analyzes public opinion about this phenomenon within the country and in the global society, examines the relationship between the introduction of the EG and the age of citizens.

The author examines the conditions that are necessary for the productive use of Internet technologies in politics, explores the mechanisms for stimulating citizens to form a civic position, and understands the benefits of using ICT for the realization of their political rights and interests.

In conclusion, it was concluded that for the effective implementation of the concept of e-government, it is necessary to take into account not only the technological and financial capabilities of society but also the type of local political system and the level of political culture, as well as the availability of information and education.

Key words: *Electronic Government, State, Management, ICT, Internet, Portal.*

Introduction. Public administration in modern society is inextricably linked with social processes and relationships between subjects. It is aimed at uniting, coordinating the joint activities of people and is of organizing nature. For effective interaction between the state and society, innovations in the field of public administration are needed, it is necessary to use the most modern information and management technologies. Any state that seeks to remain an influential subject of world politics cannot ignore, without prejudice to itself and its citizens, the most important trends in the formation of the society in the 21st century. The effective use of information and communication technologies, and above all the Internet, is in this context the most important factor in the development of society.

One of such complex innovations in the field of public administration is the widespread introduction and effective use of information and communication technologies, including those called “electronic government”.

Publications overview. The concept of e-Government has become relevant over the past decade. Due to the short period of development, this topic has not yet been fully studied therefore fundamental theoretical and methodological works on the formation and functioning of e-government are not enough. In most cases, information on this topic is reflected in the periodical literature. Publications by S. Bhogal, G. Stauers, M. Gasco, D. Lenihan, K. O’Tul are devoted to the problem of the formation and development of electronic government. Theoretical and methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of e-government projects are considered in the works of S. Yang-Jin, K. Sin-Te, M. Korski, H. Guo, R. Davidreich, and others. Analysis of the degree of scientific development of this subject area indicates insufficient knowledge of the mechanisms and relations arising in the process of creating and functioning of electronic government.

The purpose of this article is an attempt to investigate the implementation of the concept of EP as an example of the modernization of public administration.

The research problem can be formulated in the form of a question: what hinders the development of EDS in the political space of Georgia?

Research objectives:

- Show the innovative aspects of public administration in the context of EDS
- To indicate the level of development of the EDS in different regions of Georgia;
- Compare the pace of development of digital systems in different areas of management;
- To identify the reasons for the uneven use of the advantages of the EP in the practice of public administration.

Main Body. Today, information and communication technologies are developing rapidly and are being introduced into various spheres of society.

Electronic government – today, especially in a pandemic, is a famous phrase. It is seen as the main tool for modernizing government in the 21st century. The transfer of the work of officials to the world of the Internet gives rise to expectations of a radical change in the order of interaction of the public sector with citizens and business.

It is expected that the creation of e-government will increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the executive functions of the state (especially with regard to the provision of public services), make the government more transparent and accountable to citizens and businesses; will change the relationship between the state and citizens through significant changes in the level of democracy.

Consideration of e-government as an activity focused on meeting the needs of the population and business is rather narrow. Internet-based electoral voting, driver license renewals, tax reporting, house calls are just a tiny list of the wide range of e-government options.

Electronic government, according to S. Dan Sandor, is not limited to relations between the state and citizens (or business). It also has an internal manifestation: within the power system, different levels (central, regional, and local) and different branches (executive, legislative, judicial) must also interact with the use of Internet technologies as part of the process of providing public services.

Functionally, the activity of e-government can be divided into three components - the state for the state (the provision of services by the state body for other administrative bodies), the state for citizens (the provision of public services for the population) the state for business (the provision of public services for business entities).

The abbreviations of these components are also generally accepted - G2G (government to government); G2C (government to citizens); G2B (government to business).

R. Abuladze distinguishes four components and considers e-government as “a complex of organizational and technical means of interaction between the state and citizens (the system of relations G2C, Government-to-Citizen), business (G2B, Government-to-Business), civil servants (G2E, Government -to-Employees) and individual authorities (G2G, Government-to-Government)”.

The terms e-government, e-government, and e-government are often used interchangeably. At the same time, there is a difference between these concepts.

So for example, the electronic state is considered as a way of organizing state power based on the use of information and communication technologies and contains three components:

- Electronic government,
- Electronic parliament;
- Electronic justice.

In our opinion, the e-government should not be considered as a process of public administration using information and communication technologies. Here we agree with the opinion

of UN experts¹ that in the practice of using the term e-government, the subject (subjects) of management (e-government) is often mixed with the forms, processes, and technologies of management.

The introduction of information and communication technologies into the activities of public authorities is not an end in itself. The purpose of e-government is to improve the efficiency of public administration, simplify the interaction between government agencies, and simplify the interaction between the state and citizens, and organizations.

According to the definition of the consulting company Gartner Group, e-government is “the transformation of internal and external relations of government organizations based on the use of the capabilities of the Internet, information and telecommunication technologies in order to optimize the services provided, increase the level of public participation in public administration and improve internal processes”.

According to A. Chaco, e-government is part of a broader concept of e-government and can be defined as the use of information technology in government work for the benefit of “consumers” (citizens and business), as well as for their own needs. To be effective, e-government must focus on meeting the needs of citizens. Its aim should be to provide wider access to information and a fairer distribution of the services provided to society.

The relationship between the concepts of e-government and e-government is also discussed in the work of OECD e-Government Studies.²

He distinguishes between e-government and e-government according to the degree of public participation and notes that e-government involves multiple stakeholders using the Internet in government and policy implementation. However, the programs of government activities in most countries in the field of e-government are mainly related to the provision of public services online. Such a narrow application of modern information and communication technologies serves mainly operations between government bodies and citizens and does not stimulate the latter to participate in the discussion of public policy.

Thus, the creation of e-government involves the creation of e-government, the development of various forms of interaction, and the involvement of various participants.

In general, four areas of e-government manifestation can be distinguished.

1. Electronic services (e-services). This term refers to the electronic provision of government information, programs, policies, and services. They are available 24 hours a day, seven days a week. It also includes the provision of electronic services, e-administration, and innovations such as a one-stop service bureau and “one-stop-shop” access to multiple services.

2. Electronic management (e-management) concerns internal information systems that support the management and administrative functions of government agencies, including data and information management, electronic records, and information flow between departments. E-government is somewhat difficult when the government is organized around the principle of allocating work to different sectoral areas of responsibility. E-governance requires a new organizational culture, as well as a staff orientation towards performance, customer service, and citizen participation. The solution to the problems of electronic management lies in the plane of adaptation and integration of processes taking place in internal departments that do not work directly with the public.

3. Electronic democracy (e-democracy). This manifestation of e-government is the hardest to induce and contain. E-democracy is the use of information and communication technologies as a tool to help set public policy agendas and priorities, formulate policies and participate in their

¹ UN e-Government Knowledgebase; <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/about/unegovdd-framework>

² Future of e-government; <https://www.oecd.org/gov/digital-government/42547008.pdf>

implementation in a consultative manner (for example, through e-consultation or e-voting). This includes activities that increase citizen participation, including virtual city meetings, open meetings, feedback gathering, opinion polls, and community forums. Usually, after the successful implementation of e-government at the local level, citizens can form alliances on the Internet-based on this or that attitude to a particular problem.

4. Electronic commerce (e-commerce) is the concept of that side of government interaction with the outside world, which directly concerns business. E-commerce involves exchanging money for government goods or services over the Internet. For example, citizens can pay taxes or pay utility bills, renew vehicle registrations or pay for recreational programs, and the government can purchase office supplies (through e-government procurement).

E-government will not be realized if the government buys additional computers and builds a website. This will only make it possible to automate part of the administrative activity and take it out of the “paper world”. Rather, e-government is a process of government transformation; it requires planning, political will, and a steady flow of necessary resources. Neither the purchase of more advanced technologies nor the automation of complex procedures, by themselves, will be able to increase the efficiency of public administration or the level of participation of the population in public life. Technological innovations will not change the mentality of officials who do not view the citizen as a consumer of government services or as a participant in the political decision-making process.

According to J. Dempsey, e-government is the use of information and communication technologies to transform government in order to make it more accessible to citizens, more effective, and more accountable.

According to this definition, it includes:

- Providing more complete access to information via the Internet (laws, bills, other normative legal acts, forms of necessary documents, as well as economic and scientific data);
- Promoting civic participation in public life by creating opportunities for more convenient interaction with officials through electronic channels, for example, providing the ability to fill out the required documents in electronic form;
- Increasing the accountability of the government by increasing the transparency of its operations, which reduces the risks of corruption;
- Supporting the achievement of development goals by reducing the time and material costs incurred by small businesses in connection with communication with government agencies.

The organizer in the formation of the information society and the system of “electronic government” in the state, where e-signature is the electronic interaction between the government and the people. Through “electronic government” the state responds to citizens in a convenient, accessible, and understandable format. The provision of information interaction between the authorities and society has received the name “electronic government” (e-Government). According to Sh. Doghonadze, the direct translation of “e-Government” is not entirely correct, since “it is clear that we mean not only the network infrastructure of the executive branch but in general the entire infrastructure of state power and management”.

The emergence of EDS is associated with the transfer of public administration to the technologies of the information society, where EDS becomes an instrument of state and administrative reform. Many developing countries saw e-government as an opportunity to significantly reduce the gap with industrialized countries through the modernization of public administration.

The main idea of this project is to practically achieve changes in the system of executive authorities in order to increase the level of their functioning, information openness, and optimal

provision of public services. ICTs provide an opportunity to move to a modern model of democracy, in which access to information, the possibility of direct participation in the management of state and non-state structures will become available to all citizens who will not need traditional national media. Information technologies can radically change modern culture, morality, politics, transform the perception of time and space.

The dissemination and accessibility of ICT is a prerequisite for the democratization of society, the development of civic initiatives, and the self-organization of people. Being the most important means of communication, new technologies are used to inform citizens on a wide range of issues of various types of life, to discuss bills and other legal acts in the process of their preparation and development of political decisions. Communication on the basis of the Internet has moved to a new level of its development, and the authorities need such an innovation in the first place. Some researchers suggest considering the Internet as a political institution as a stable environment for the interaction of policy actors.

The introduction of electronic signatures requires joint efforts of both the state apparatus and public organizations, business structures, and ordinary citizens. E-government and corporate information technology architecture provides the necessary ingredients to achieve the desired goal, which is the successful implementation of applied information systems for e-government, which, in turn, will provide the required efficiency and responsibility in the performance of public administration functions.

According to the summary of statistical data that determine the share of citizens using the www.gov.ge website in all regions of Georgia, it can be seen that the portal is most in-demand in Tbilisi and the Kvemo Kartli region (55,1% of the population). Experts attribute this situation to the fact that the regional authorities pay great attention to the transfer of public services to electronic form. Tbilisi, despite its status as a capital, was only in 2nd place (54,7%), and Batumi and Kutaisi took 3-rd (54,2%) and 4-th (52,8) lines, respectively. This is due to the fact that these subjects of Georgia have their own portals.

In our opinion, the state of affairs in the constituent entities largely depends on the position of the authorities. Most of the popular government services today can already be obtained in electronic form. Regional authorities should pay special attention only to the observance of the safety rules of operation and the issues of compliance with the rules of communication in a pandemic, established by the Ministry of Health and Social Security of Georgia.

To remove certain obstacles, the Georgian government provides information to the population. The main informants about public services are SMS mailings, print and television media, the Internet, information booklets, etc. The popularization of e-services can also be facilitated by various campaigns.

For example, a shorter waiting period for a service when submitting an application via the Internet, compared to contacting a public service center, a discount on cellular payments, etc.

However, the solution to the issue of popularizing electronic signatures among the population is not the only reason for the increase in the number of users of the public services portal. For example, if you pay attention to the phenomenon of electronic government in Georgia, you will notice that the electronic signature is gaining momentum here very quickly. During its existence, the electronic government has overcome four stages of formation and development, was positively accepted and highly appreciated by the world community – this is evidenced by high positions in international and national ratings, nominations in competitions. The level of development of the Georgian e-government is assessed as “developing” and is considered one of the most successful.

However, despite such achievements, the country still has a rather low level of computer literacy, especially in mountainous and sparsely populated regions. Not all of the population has an

understanding of digital technologies and has the skills to work with the Internet. And mostly, of course, these are young people, who, as a rule, use government services very rarely and not in full. The older generation still prefers to receive public services in an old-fashioned way, for example, through public service centers or making mandatory payments through cash registers. Naturally, spending a lot of your time on it. But with the pandemic, this type of service has become inaccessible. Everything, from obtaining any certificate and ending with registration for vaccination against COVID-19, is available to the citizens of Georgia mainly in digital format.

Conclusion. For the productive use of Internet technologies in politics, additional motivation is needed. Therefore, the institutions of political socialization, along with the formation of the civic position of the individual, should help citizens understand the benefits of using modern information and communication technologies in the implementation of their political rights and interests. Obviously, a significant place in this process is given to political education. Personally-oriented and research teaching methods combined with the potential of information, communication and training functions of information and communication technologies can become a kind of virtual training for the preparation of “electronic citizens”.

“Electronic government” is a modern tool for improving public administration and relations between the state and society. But for the effectiveness of the introduction of “electronic government”, not only the technological and financial capabilities of society are taken into account, but also the nature of the political system, the level of the political culture of the population, the level of accessibility of information and education.

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